

Studies on Some *N*-Acyl *N*-Phenylhydroxylamines as Metal-Complexing Ligands. Part III.

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In previous communications^{1,2} the syntheses of *N*-*o*, *m*, *p*-nitrobenzoyl and monochloroacetyl *N*-phenylhydroxylamines and some metal complexes with those ligands and also with *N*-acetyl derivative have been reported. The co-ordinating abilities of these ligands as well as the *N*-benzoyl derivative have been studied by determining the stability constants of some of the metal chelates formed with them. Since the evaluation of stability constant requires the knowledge of the acid dissociation constants of the ligands, they have been determined in (1 : 1) aqueous acetone as most of them are not soluble in water. The acid dissociation constants of the corresponding carboxylic acids have also been measured under the identical conditions to trace the relation between the acid dissociation constants of the carboxylic acids and the corresponding *N*-acyl *N*-phenylhydroxylamines.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were either A.R. quality or properly purified.

Measurements were performed in (1 : 1) aqueous acetone by titrating potentiometrically, reagent solutions of strength $1.5-3.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ containing free perchloric acid with a standard NaOH solution. The ionic strength of the medium ($\mu = 0.5$) was kept constant by adding requisite quantity of sodium perchlorate.

pH measurements were made with a Cambridge *pH*-meter (portable type). Electrode system consisted of a glass electrode and a saturated calomel reference electrode with a 2*M* sodium nitrate solution bridge. The results reported here are based on duplicate titrations made under identical conditions.

In order to determine the final acid concentration, a graphical method³ was employed. For this purpose *pH* values of a number of HClO₄ solutions of known strength in (1 : 1) aqueous acetone and having the same ionic strength ($\mu = 0.5$) were noted. *pH* values were plotted against negative logarithm of the acid concentration. The final acid concentrations were extrapolated from the corresponding *pH* assuming that the behaviour of the strong acids is the same in aqueous and mixed solvents.

The experiments were carried out at $30 \pm 1^\circ$. The values of \bar{n} (average number of hydrogen bound per molecule) were then calculated and plotted against *pH*. The acid dissociation constant has been finally evaluated from the *pH* corresponding to $\bar{n} = 0.05$.

1. N. N. Ghosh and G. Siddhanta, *This Journal*, 1968, **45**, 1049.
2. N. N. Ghosh and G. Siddhanta, *This Journal*, 1969, **46**, 488.
3. N. N. Ghosh and M. N. Majumder, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 559.

pK values obtained are stated in Table I. The acidity of the *N*-acyl *N*-phenylhydroxylamines is found in the order *o*-nitrobenzoyl- > monochloreacetyl- > *p*-nitrobenzoyl- > *m*-nitrobenzoyl- > acetyl-derivative.

TABLE I

<i>N</i> -Acyl <i>N</i> -Phenylhydroxylamines	pK^*	Carboxylic acids	pK'
<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CON(Ph)OH	9.20	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COOH	3.95
ClCH ₂ CON(Ph)OH	9.26	ClCH ₂ COOH	4.05
<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CON(Ph)OH	9.41	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COOH	4.60
<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CON(Ph)OH	9.44	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ COOH	4.66
C ₆ H ₅ CON(Ph)OH	9.82	C ₆ H ₅ COOH	5.68
CH ₃ CON(Ph)OH	10.11	CH ₃ COOH	6.00

DISCUSSION

The order of variation of pK values of *N*-acyl *N*-phenylhydroxylamines parallels that of the corresponding carboxylic acids. As is observed by several workers in this field^{4,5}, the pK^* values of the *N*-acyl *N*-phenylhydroxylamines are found to have a linear relation with pK' values of the corresponding carboxylic acids except the *N*-acetyl derivative.

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4. L. P. Hammet, "Physical Chemistry", McGraw Hill, New York, (1940).
5. R. L. Dutta and S. Ghosh, *This Journal*, 1967, **44**, 820.